

A comparative analysis of U.S. micromobility usage with built environment and socioeconomic factors

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Shared micromobility services, such as e-scooters and e-bicycles, have experienced remarkable growth in recent years. This growth highlights an increasing reliance on micromobility systems for short distance trips within cities, as a first-mile/last-mile solution. My research examines patterns in micromobility trip characteristics within and across five U.S. cities— Baltimore, Denver, Detroit, Portland, and Washington. This work also investigates whether these patterns reflect differences in built environment (BE) or socioeconomic and demographics (SED) between cities or if they provide unique insights into city dynamics.

Cities are influenced by their unique historical and economic development, along with urban planning decisions. As a result, they may have distinct BE or SED compositions. These variations can add complexity in understanding similarities and differences among cities. Micromobility trip characteristics can offer a dynamic perspective on the similarities and differences between cities. Previous studies have examined variations in micromobility usage across cities to understand their relationship with BE and SED characteristics [1, 2, 3], and how these differences contribute to variations in usage patterns. These studies examine BE and SED attributes associated with e-scooter usage, but do not evaluate differences in these characteristics between cities or how they relate to micromobility usage. To our knowledge, no study has quantified the multi-dimensional similarity in micromobility trips within and across cities.

To quantify multidimensional micromobility trip similarity across cities, we build a random forest (RF) model using multi-dimensional micromobility trip attributes, to determine its ability to discern trip patterns across cities. A proximity matrix of observation similarity, obtained from the RF model, is used to organize and cluster observations in a lower two-dimensional space. We repeat this process by building two additional models for the BE and SED attributes. The city label is used as the response variable across all models. Clusters resulting from the micromobility, BE, and SED RF models are used to evaluate differences between cities.

In determining differences between cities based on micromobility trip patterns, we find that our micromobility-based city prediction model is able to decipher between most cities using micromobility trip characteristics. The model yields five distinct clusters of micromobility trip patterns, which can be characterized by varied trip activity, distances, and durations. We compare proportions of clusters within each city and find that cities with similar micromobility compositions also share similar spatial distributions of micromobility activity. The built environment and socioeconomic and demographic models outperform the micromobility model, suggesting that cities have more unique BE and SED characteristics, as compared to their micromobility trip patterns.

Micromobility trip patterns offer a unique perspective into city similarities, providing insights that complement the BE and SED characteristics observed. Models developed in this study show that some cities have distinct micromobility trip compositions and spatial distributions, while others exhibit more varied patterns. These findings offer a dynamic perspective that can assist transport planners in developing policies by drawing from cities with similar mobility patterns, BE characteristics, or SED profiles.

References

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